

Assessment of alternative fluid calibration to estimate traceable liquefied hydrogen flow measurement uncertainty

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ABSTRACT

The usage of liquefied hydrogen (LH₂) is growing fast as the EU aims to be climate-neutral by 2050. Therefore, reliable and consistent measurements of LH₂ amounts (as determined by flow meters) will become increasingly important for custody transfers. Reliability and consistency of measurements is established from calibration. Due to the lack of facilities being able to calibrate flow meters directly with LH₂ as calibration fluid, the question arises whether the measurement error of the calibration performed on a different fluid and different process conditions are representative for the errors when measuring LH₂. An on-site calibration of two turbine meters measuring LH₂ flow was performed. A Coriolis mass flow meter calibrated on water was used as a reference in conjunction with a dedicated flow meter model, which was validated by a directly SI-traceable calibration on liquefied natural gas. LH₂ flow rates were within 1000 kg/h and 3000 kg/h, which are relevant to hydrogen transport by LH₂ trailers. The analysis of the measurement data reveal errors on totalized mass ranging from 2.0 % to 2.9 % with a total calibration uncertainty of 1.3 % ($k = 2$), where the main uncertainty source was identified as the on-site density estimate necessary to convert the volume flow measurements into mass flow measurements. The results indicate the need for reliable and accurate temperature measurements (the latter allowing for an accurate density estimate), so that volume based and mass based amount measurements can be compared with smaller uncertainties.

1. Introduction

The EU aims to be climate-neutral by 2050 — an economy with net-zero greenhouse gas emissions. This objective is at the heart of the European Green Deal [1] and in line with the EU's commitment to global climate action under the Paris Agreement (COP21). The hydrogen strategy for a climate neutral Europe [2] identifies liquefied hydrogen (LH₂) as a means of energy transport to reach the Green Deal objective. The usage of LH₂ is thus growing fast, and transportation sectors are pushing towards this solution (aircraft, liquefied hydrogen carriers, trains). In a similar fashion to trading natural gas or oil, the widespread use of LH₂ will need to be supported by reliable and consistent measurements to determine amounts of LH₂ traded during custody transfer. Flow meters are customarily employed during the custody transfer process to determine the amount transferred when transporting resources from a seller to a buyer. Reliability and consistency of flow meter measurements is established from calibration of flow meters, which inherently entails the establishment of a direct link with the SI-units. The calibration is typically performed in dedicated laboratories accredited to the ISO/IEC 17025 documentary standard [3].

Given the physical working principle of a flow meter the measurement error of that flow meter may be influenced by the physical properties of the fluid flowing through it and its specific process conditions (e.g., temperature of the atmosphere surrounding the pipe in which the flow meter is installed). Turbine meters turn the axial motion of fluid flow into a rotational motion through turbine blades and then generate pulses at a speed proportional to the volume flowrate. Their measurement error at LH₂ conditions can be affected from the meter bodies' contraction. Böckler et al. [4] provide an example of water and liquefied natural gas (LNG) calibrations of a 2" turbine flow meter showing that, at given Reynolds number, the K-factor (pulses per liter) as obtained on water does not completely coincide with the K-factor on LNG. Coriolis flow meter measurements originate from the Coriolis force appearing in the meters' oscillating tube(s) when the fluid mass passes through. It gives rise to a time-dependent deflection of the tube(s) which are picked up by the meters' sensing elements. The deflections are proportional to the mass flow rate and the stiffness of the measuring tube(s). The stiffness, in turn, is temperature-dependent so that Coriolis flow meter measurement error can be affected at

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LH₂ temperature conditions (i.e., $-253\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at atmospheric pressure). Jonge et al. [5] show results of Coriolis mass flow meter flow rate measurements at liquefied helium conditions ($-269\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) indicating flow rate errors of about 1 % for flow rates up to 0.03 kg/s ($\pm 100\text{ kg/h}$). Due to the lack of LH₂ calibration facilities with industrial flow rates (up to 5000 kg/h), a question arises on the degree to which the measurement error of the calibration likely performed on water at ambient conditions is representative for its error when measuring LH₂ at very low temperatures ($-253\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). For LNG it is known that the flow meter error on water, as established during the water flow calibration in an ISO/IEC 17025 accredited laboratory, is not necessarily exactly the same as when using it with LNG [6,7]. The aforementioned is relevant for LH₂, since (1) both LNG and LH₂ are cryogenic fluids, and (2) the physical working principles of the flow meters used are coinciding (e.g., Coriolis, ultrasonic, or turbine). Therefore the additional measurement uncertainty of a water calibrated LH₂ flow meter in a LH₂ flow measuring environment must be (quantitatively) investigated. Determination of LH₂ flow meter accuracy is needed to ensure safe and reliable LH₂ transport and is identified by Saif et al. [8] as one of the key research and demonstration priorities for progressing the hydrogen supply chain. Monahan et al. [9] report estimation of a two-phase (gas/liquid) prototype mass flow meter within a 10 % tolerance and potential to use it in a cryogenic application. Shaaban [10] performs numerical simulations to design a constriction type flow meter optimized for use in LH₂ conditions. However, research into, and demonstration of, accuracy of LH₂ custody transfer through measurement by LH₂ flow meters is, to the best knowledge of the authors, currently not reported in the literature.

In this paper, Coriolis mass flow meter (CMF) models will be employed and combined with direct SI-traceable calibrations on water and LNG of a single CMF to quantitatively estimate the achievable, (indirect) SI-traceable flow measurement uncertainty of LH₂ CMFs. LH₂ flow experimental results will be presented in which the calibrated CMF, with its base uncertainty, was used as a reference in the calibration of turbine meters along the same flow line. Inherent to the calibration another (larger) uncertainty of the LH₂ turbine meter error is presented. The results presented are directly relevant to LH₂ trailer (un)loading in transport applications as the flow rates considered are ranging from 1000 kg/h to 3000 kg/h. The presented errors and associated measurement uncertainties provide novel quantitative indications of achievable accuracy during LH₂ custody transfer.

A literature survey was performed into the (publicly available) analytical models for CMFs [11]. Two analytical models were found, one for a straight tube [12] and one for a U-shape CMF [13]. Combining the results of a CMF calibration on water and the available analytical models presented in [12,13], Wu [14,15] estimated an uncertainty budget for LNG measurements of 0.20 % (coverage factor $k = 2$) and 0.24 % ($k = 2$) for a straight tube and for a U-shape CMF, respectively. To the best knowledge of the authors, no similar work has been done for LH₂ measurements aside from the patent recently published by Patten and Garnett [16], which is applicable to generic CMF's shapes and thus to our case study where a delta-shape CMF was used to take the measurements, for which no analytical model was found in the literature. Therefore, here two analytical meter models applicable to CMF's measurements from Patten and Garnett's patent [16] are employed to propagate the uncertainties of the quantities that appear in the analytical equation using the Monte Carlo method according to the Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement — Supplement 1 [17]. Each of the influencing variables is carefully analyzed to provide the best available quantitative information of its uncertainty.

This paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides information about the experimental setup. Section 3 lists in detail how each uncertainty component has been estimated and thus contributes to the final uncertainty budget. The findings and subsequent discussion and conclusions are detailed in Sections 4, 5 and 6 respectively.

Table 1LH₂ CMF100 calibration results using water and LNG as alternative calibration fluids.

Calibration fluid	Reference flow kg/s	Error %	Expanded uncertainty U %
Water	0.5104	0.019	0.017
Water	0.7644	0.017	0.017
Water	1.0282	0.016	0.017
Water	1.2844	0.017	0.017
Water	1.5366	0.015	0.017
Water	1.8114	0.016	0.017
Water	2.0615	0.008	0.017
Water	3.8964	0.006	0.017
LNG	2.016	-0.26	0.18
LNG	1.674	-0.26	0.18
LNG	1.246	-0.25	0.18
LNG	0.831	-0.23	0.18
LNG	0.497	-0.23	0.31
LNG	0.624	-0.25	0.31

Fig. 1. LH₂ CMF100 calibration results using water and LNG as alternative calibration fluids. Water calibration results are obtained from Emerson's ISO/IEC 17025 accredited calibration laboratory. LNG results are obtained in VSL's SI-traceable calibration facility. Calibration uncertainty is indicated by the error (uncertainty, $k = 2$) bars (water uncertainty is small with respect to the symbol size). The manufacturer's specification is obtained from the CMF's data sheet [18] and includes the zero specification at 0.47 kg/h.

2. Experimental

A commercially available LH₂ CMF100 (nominal flow rate on water at about 16,000 kg/h) flow meter (manufacturer Emerson) was tested with water in Emerson's ISO/IEC 17025 accredited calibration laboratory and with LNG in VSL's SI-traceable calibration facility. This provided the flow meter with SI-traceability directly to mass flow units with so-called alternative fluids (i.e., fluids different from LH₂, like water and LNG). Fig. 1 and Table 1 show calibration results of a CMF100. For this flow meter, the error on water is at around 0.015 % of reference mass flow rate, while it is at about $-0.25\text{ }%$ on LNG. During the LNG calibration, the meter was insulated and the temperatures ranged from $-171\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $-166\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The meter's material compatibility at LH₂ temperatures ($-253\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) was carefully checked.

The setup of the LH₂ flow experiments is depicted in Fig. 2. LH₂ flow is created from setting a driving pressure in the gas phase of the storage tank. Two turbine meter measurements (approximate maximum flow rate at 45000 kg/h) are combined with their pressure and temperature measurements into a reference mass flow rate using a computed LH₂ density (assuming 100 % parahydrogen) for the conversion of volume flow rate to mass flow rate. These two turbine meters are calibrated on water on an annual basis. The calibrated CMF was installed at the connecting flange of the test bench (Fig. 3). A flexible hose was used to guide the LH₂ to the stack where the hydrogen was then flared. An orifice was installed to ensure sufficient pressure for the hydrogen to remain in liquefied state. The CMF and return line were carefully insulated with Armaflex, which was wrapped tightly around the piping. The zero was set at ambient conditions and it was ensured that with a cooled down line the zero specification at 0.47 kg/h was met.

Fig. 2. Schematic of LH₂ experiments at the Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt (DLR).

Fig. 3. Picture of the CMF100 (1) as installed during LH₂ flow tests. Also displayed are: flow direction (arrows), pressure measurement port (2), temperature measurement position (3), flexible hose (4), (location of) orifice (5).

Table 2

Overview of measurement batches. Run time reported is as recorded by the CMF data acquisition system. Repeat #4 is crossed out as TAOs created unsteady flow conditions.

Repeat #	Flow rate		Run time s
	kg/s	kg/h	
1	0.769	2769	29.407
2	0.494	1777	43.107
3	0.326	1172	84.949
4	0.772	2780	33.838
5	0.498	1791	63.250
6	0.331	1193	93.479
7	0.766	2759	34.569
8	0.491	1766	64.801
9	0.329	1184	91.952
10	0.766	2756	32.814
11	0.491	1767	48.241
12	0.329	1184	104.162
13	0.329	1185	91.567
14	0.494	1779	61.593
15	0.770	2771	34.407

The overview of measurement batches is displayed in Table 2. A single measurement batch was run per flow point, and this sequence was followed sequentially. A typical calibration procedure is to take several measurement batches per nominal flow point (starting at the highest flow), after which the second-to-highest flow is set to again take several repeats. The unconventional order as displayed in the Table 2 was chosen to (1) be able to adjust the test protocol in case of issues during the measurements without running out of stored LH₂ and (2) to potentially investigate if the order itself affects the measurement error (c.f., repeats 10–15). The lowest flow point at around 1180 kg/h is relatively high with respect to the minimal flow rate at which the CMF100 (at about 400 kg/h) fulfills manufacturers specifications at ambient conditions. The reason is that sufficient flow is required in order to avoid boil-off of LH₂ during the batch. Avoidance of boil-off could not be ensured at flow rates below 1150 kg/h. Boil-off of LH₂ would create a gas/liquid mixture at which point the quality of the measurements could not be ensured. It was made sure that the drive-gain of the CMF100 remained sufficiently low to indicate the absence of significant boil-off, and thus the presence of single-phase flow, during the measurements. Furthermore, it was checked that during the measurements the temperature of the liquid hydrogen was at least 3 K lower than the temperature at the saturated liquid line at the given pressure. Prior to the measurement batches, a small batch (few seconds) LH₂ flow higher than the set point was created just before the batch to ensure the avoidance of Thermal Acoustic Oscillations (TAO) [19] created within the appendages of Fig. 2 flow line. For repeat number 4 this was not performed and it was shown to create TAO's manifesting as strong flow oscillations. Lastly, we remark that the measurements of the turbine meter have been collected using the data acquisition system of the facility, which recorded a data point every 0.001 s on average, while the measurements of the CMF have been recorded with the data acquisition system of the CMF itself, which recorded every 0.05 s on average. Therefore, an additional uncertainty source due to the difference in the sampling interval should be considered in the uncertainty analysis.

3. Theory

3.1. Analytical CMF models for LH₂ measurements

The relationship between mass flow rate and the flow measurement of a CMF is dependent on the temperature of the fluid being measured. A linear temperature compensation was developed to compensate for varying temperature conditions, but when CMF were first applied to cryogenic applications, it was noticed that at extremely low temperatures the elastic properties of the steel behave non-linearly [20] and

this in turn affects the tube's stiffness. Thus a correction was developed for cryogenic applications down to -233 °C

$$\dot{m} = FCF(\Delta t - \Delta t_0)(\phi_0 + \phi_1 \Delta T + \phi_2 \Delta T^2 + \phi_3 \Delta T^3 + \phi_4 \Delta T^4), \quad (1)$$

where \dot{m} [SI-unit: kg/s] is the mass flow rate, FCF [kg/s²] is the flow calibration factor determined during the water calibration at laboratory conditions (i.e., 20 °C and atmospheric pressure), Δt [s] is the fundamental Coriolis time measurement, Δt_0 [s] is the Δt value at no-flow conditions, ΔT [K] is the temperature difference in K with respect to 273.15 K and is defined negative for $T < 273.15$ K, and ϕ_0 [K⁰], ..., ϕ_4 [K⁻⁴] are polynomial coefficients that characterize the nonlinear Young's modulus behavior.

Temperature has an important effect also on the geometry of the meter itself. As the temperature increases (decreases), the steel expands (shrinks) thus modifying the geometric parameters of the meter. Therefore, an additional correction term is added to Eq. (1) as follows

$$\dot{m} = FCF(\Delta t - \Delta t_0)(\phi_0 + \phi_1 \Delta T + \phi_2 \Delta T^2 + \phi_3 \Delta T^3 + \phi_4 \Delta T^4)(1 + \alpha \Delta T), \quad (2)$$

where α [K⁻¹] is the thermal expansion coefficient normalized with respect to 293.15 K, i.e., the ambient temperature during a water calibration in a laboratory.

Recently a method to compensate the mass flow measurement of CMFs using the fluid density and the drive frequency instead of the Young's modulus has been patented [16]. According to this method, the mass flow rate is calculated as

$$\dot{m} = FCF(\Delta t - \Delta t_0) \frac{\rho_f(1 + \alpha \Delta T)^3 + C_2}{K^2 C_1}, \quad (3)$$

where ρ_f [kg/m³] is the density of the fluid being measured, K [s] is the tube period, and

$$C_1 = \frac{D_2 - D_1}{K_2^2 - K_1^2} \quad C_2 = K_1^2 \frac{D_2 - D_1}{K_2^2 - K_1^2}$$

are calibration constants, where D_1 [kg/m³] and D_2 [kg/m³] are the density values of air and of water, respectively, at laboratory conditions and K_1 [s] and K_2 [s] are the tube periods measured by the CMF when measuring air or water, respectively.

In the remainder of this paper we will refer to Eq. (2) as the *stiffness correction model* and to Eq. (3) as the *density correction model*. In the next section we evaluate the standard uncertainty associated to Eqs. (2) and (3) for LH₂ measurements.

3.2. Uncertainty evaluation

In order to estimate the standard uncertainty associated to the stiffness and to the density correction model, we combine the contribution of several uncertainty sources. Uncertainty sources that apply to both models are: repeatability, zero stability, pressure and temperature effects, timing (i.e., Δt), calibration constants and thermal expansion. Specific to the density correction model there are additional uncertainties associated to density and to the tube period, while the stiffness correction model has an additional uncertainty source given by the Young's modulus. In what follows, we describe how each uncertainty source has been treated and estimated.

3.2.1. Repeatability

CMF's repeatability uncertainty for water measurements is included in the total calibration uncertainty and thus already included in the uncertainty associated to the FCF, see Section 3.2.6.

3.2.2. Zero stability

According to the manufacturer specifications, the zero specification (z.s.) of a CMF100 is 0.47 kg/h [18]. We treat this number as the half-width of a uniform distribution and compute the percent error with respect to the lowest flow rate measured during the test (0.33 kg/s) as a worst case scenario estimate. In fact, looking at the formula for percent error at the flow rate of interest, i.e.,

$$e_{zero} = \frac{z.s.}{\dot{m}} \cdot 100 \%$$

it is evident that the highest relative error due to zero stability is obtained at the lowest flow rate. Thus the standard uncertainty due to zero stability is estimated as $u_{zero} \approx 0.02 \%$ at $\dot{m} = 0.33 \text{ kg/s}$.

3.2.3. Pressure

It is well known that larger flow meters have a pressure dependency [21] and recent studies found that the effect due to pressure is in general agreement with the manufacturer's specification [13,22]. During the LH₂ measurements, the CMF software automatically applied a pressure correction based on a pre-set pressure for each setpoint. Therefore the pressure uncertainty contribution is due to differences between the pressure measured by the pressure sensor of the facility in correspondence of the CMF and the pressure set in CMF software. We estimate the expanded uncertainty due to the pressure correction as $U_p = |c_p(\text{measured pressure} - \text{set pressure})|$ where $c_p = -0.003 \%$ /bar is the pressure correction factor. The standard uncertainty contribution $u_p = U_p/2$ varies slightly between repeats and it has been estimated to be approximately 0.0009 % in the worst case. We remark that in this derivation the pressure measurement uncertainty, the pressure drop across the CMF, and the uncertainty in the pressure correction factor specified by the manufacturer are assumed negligible.

3.2.4. Temperature

Temperature is arguably the most important uncertainty source since it affects other quantities such as density, Young's modulus and thermal expansion, and is also present by itself in both correction model equations. VSL's LNG facility calibration data show a maximum error of 3 K in the temperature readings of insulated CMF meters. As the temperature difference between ambient temperature around the pipe and cryogenic flow temperature within the pipe increases, errors in the temperature measurement are expected to increase. Therefore, we considered a maximum error of 5 K (half-width of a uniform distribution) for the temperature measurements at LH₂ operating conditions, which coincides with the statement in the patent [16]. Such assumption corresponds to a standard uncertainty $u_T = 5/\sqrt{3} \approx 2.89 \text{ K}$ for the temperature measurements of an insulated CMF.

3.2.5. Timing

The CMF has a time resolution in the order of picoseconds and its timing uncertainty is considered to be negligible.

3.2.6. Calibration constants

One calibration constant that appears in both correction methods is the FCF. The uncertainty associated with the FCF is given by the total calibration uncertainty from the water calibration. Thus, for this application we have $u_{FCF} = 0.017/2 \approx 0.009 \%$.

The density correction model has two additional calibration constants, $C_1 = (D_2 - D_1) / (K_2^2 - K_1^2)$ and $C_2 = K_1^2 (D_2 - D_1) / (K_2^2 - K_1^2)$. The uncertainty in D_1 (D_2) is given by the accuracy in measuring the density of air (water), which has been estimated as 0.09 kg/m³ (0.08 kg/m³) and are treated as standard uncertainty of a normal distribution. A linear extrapolation is then performed to the nominal values $D_1 = 0 \text{ g/cm}^3$ and $D_2 = 1 \text{ g/cm}^3$ for easiness of presentation. Since the air (water) density is (very) close to the nominal value 0 (1), we consider the extrapolation uncertainty to be negligible. We consider negligible also the uncertainty in K_1 and K_2 since their estimation is based on time measurements which are significantly more accurate than the density measurements. When propagating the uncertainty in D_1 and D_2 we get an uncertainty of 0.012 % for C_1 and C_2 .

3.2.7. Thermal expansion

The thermal expansion of the material of the flow meter is usually modeled as a percentage linear expansion which, for stainless steel 316 in the temperature range 4–293 K, is given by the NIST's model available in [23]. At $T = 20 \text{ K}$ the mean value of the dimensionless thermal expansion coefficient α is 0.99696 [23] with an associated expanded uncertainty $U_\alpha = 0.015 \%$. Thus the standard uncertainty is $u_\alpha \approx 0.008 \%$, assuming a normal distribution. For more details see [11].

3.2.8. Density

In Patten and Garnett's patent [16] it is mentioned that ideally the density should be estimated using an equation of state (EOS) that takes as input temperature, pressure and composition. Therefore we use the software TREND 5.0 [24] to estimate the density of the fluid given temperature, pressure and composition. In particular, we use the EOS from Leachman et al. [25] to estimate the density of pure hydrogen, where we assume that it is 100 % parahydrogen. We estimated the uncertainties in the density due to uncertainties in the input values using the numerical approximation described in the Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement [26], where we assume that the uncertainties in temperature, pressure and composition are mutually independent. We then combine the so-obtained uncertainty with the uncertainty of the EOS itself.

Also in this case we considered a maximum error of 5 K (half-width of a uniform distribution) for the temperature sensors, which corresponds to a standard uncertainty $u_T = 5/\sqrt{3} \approx 2.89 \text{ K}$ for the temperature measurements. The temperature uncertainty results into a density uncertainty due to temperature $u_{\rho,T} \approx 3.65 \text{ kg/m}^3$ (note that the sensitivity coefficient is included in the estimated number). Regarding the pressure measurement results we considered a standard uncertainty of 1 %. The maximum density uncertainty resulting from the pressure uncertainty has been estimated as $u_{\rho,p} \approx 0.02 \text{ kg/m}^3$. To estimate the effect of impurities on the density of the fluid at given temperature and pressure, we compared the density estimate for pure liquefied hydrogen to the density estimate of liquefied hydrogen including the maximum level of impurities specified in the composition certificate from the supplier. In this calculation we had to consider normal hydrogen (instead of parahydrogen) because at the time of writing TREND 5.0 could not compute a mixture of parahydrogen and other chemical components different from hydrogen. The difference due to the presence of impurities was four orders of magnitudes smaller than the uncertainty due to temperature changes. Thus we decided to neglect this uncertainty source. Lastly, Leachman et al. [25] reports an uncertainty in density of 0.1 % at temperatures from the triple point to 250 K and at pressures up to 40 MPa. We thus set $u_{\rho,EOS} = 0.1 \%$. Combining these uncertainties according to the law of propagation of uncertainty gives the standard uncertainty for density $u_\rho \approx 3.65 \text{ kg/m}^3$, which we treat as the standard deviation of a normal distribution.

3.2.9. Tube period

The measurement of the CMF's tube period is carefully calibrated during the manufacturing process and the meter itself has been manufactured specifically for the measurement of cryogenic fluids. We propagate the tube period deviation reported in the patent [16] through the model Eq. (3), where we use the average value of the tube period during measurements instead of its nominal value. We consider this deviation as the standard deviation of a normal distribution.

3.2.10. Young's modulus

To the knowledge of the authors, Ledbetter [20] provides the only publicly available measurement data of the Young's modulus of stainless steel 316 (the material of the CMF used during the measurements). Their associated uncertainty is reported by Ledbetter [27] as $u_E = 1.9 \%$. Little information is given about how the uncertainty budget has been obtained or whether it is a standard or expanded uncertainty

Table 3

Uncertainty components of the total standard uncertainty budget of the stiffness and of the density correction models at liquefied hydrogen temperature. NA = Not Applicable. MC = Uncertainty propagated through the model equation using the Monte Carlo method [17].

Uncertainty component	Estimation source	Probability distribution	Standard uncertainty contribution (%)	
			Stiffness	Density
CMF repeatability	Included in FCF uncertainty	NA	NA	NA
CMF zero stability	Manufacturer specification	uniform	0.02	0.02
Pressure effect	Calibration data and manufacturer specification	normal	0.0009	0.0009
Temperature	Proxy from LNG facility	uniform	MC	MC
Timing	Considered negligible	NA	NA	NA
Calibration constants	Calibration data and manufacturer specification	normal	MC	MC
Thermal expansion coefficient	Literature	normal	MC	MC
Density	Propagation through EOS	normal	NA	MC
Tube period	Manufacturer specification	normal	NA	MC
Young's modulus	Literature	normal	0.5	NA

budget. A somewhat more detailed uncertainty budget has been provided by Ledbetter et al. [28] for stainless steel 304. Assuming that the uncertainty budget for stainless steel 316 has been obtained in a similar fashion as the one for stainless steel 304, we would then have to consider only the repeatability component since the steel material lot-to-lot variability is calibrated out during the calibration at ambient temperature. This assumption allows us to reduce the uncertainty associated to the Young's modulus to $u_E = 0.5\%$, which we will consider as a standard uncertainty. For more details see [11].

3.3. Uncertainty budget of stiffness and density model

To obtain an uncertainty budget of the stiffness correction model (2) and of the density (3), we propagate the uncertainties of the quantities that appear in the equation using the Monte Carlo method [17]. We then add the uncertainty contributions due to zero stability and pressure to the result of the Monte Carlo evaluation using the law of propagation of uncertainties [26]. Following this procedure we obtained a standard uncertainty $u_{E,corr} = 0.51\%$ and $u_{\rho,corr} = 0.18\%$ for the stiffness and the density correction model, respectively, where the dominant uncertainty sources are the uncertainty associated to the measurement of the Young's modulus and the density estimate (see Table 3).

3.4. On-site calibration uncertainty

When installing the CMF in the LH₂ flow facility to provide traceability to the SI-units, it is used as so-called transfer standard. On-site LH₂ total calibration uncertainty is now a function of the total calibration uncertainty of the transfer standard and on-site uncertainty sources. For instance, temperature and pressure sensors will create additional uncertainties, and using a calibrated transfer standard in an on-site facility will bring in new sources of repeatability uncertainty. Using the measurement data we estimated a repeatability standard uncertainty of 0.07% (more details in Section 4).

Since in the LH₂ measurements we are comparing meters based on different principles (volume flow rate measurements in case of the turbine meters and mass flow rate measurements in case of the CMF), we consider an additional uncertainty source due to the density estimate done by the facility. The reported uncertainty of the pressure and temperature sensors at the on-site facility are about 1% of the maximum operating pressure (16 bar) and temperature (40 K), respectively. When analyzing the data, a 0.15 K discrepancy in the zero setting of the CMF's and of the facility's temperature sensors was found. Thus the temperature uncertainty of the facility's sensors becomes $0.4 + 0.15 = 0.55$ K, which we treat as the half-width of a uniform distribution. We note that accurate temperature measurements of cryogenic fluids are challenging and a well-known issue in the literature [29–31], thus they could have large associated errors and uncertainties. We then propagate these uncertainties through the EOS to obtain (after considering also the uncertainty of the EOS) an estimate of the additional uncertainty

in the density estimate, where we assumed 100% parahydrogen as in 3.2.8. The stated temperature and pressure uncertainties resulted into an additional standard uncertainty of 0.57% in the flow rate measurement due to the on-site density uncertainty.

Other important potential uncertainty sources are so-called line pack effects and synchronization timing uncertainty. Line pack effects arise from density changes in the interconnected volume during a flow measurement batch, which we calculate as described by van der Beek et al. [32]. The line pack effect was estimated to be lower than 0.02% of mass flow rate for most runs except for repeat #4 for which it was estimated as circa 0.10%. This relatively large effect is due to the presence of TAO's during the measurements in repeat #4. Therefore we exclude the measurements of run #4 from the analysis.

Since the measurements have been recorded using two different data acquisition systems (i.e., the one of the facility for the turbine meters and the CMF's system for its own measurements), two additional uncertainty contributions have to be considered due to the synchronization timing uncertainty. The first one is due to a potential delay in the CMF's system when receiving the synchronization signal emitted by the facility equipment. Since the data acquisition system of the facility recorded the data using a countdown as time stamp (without recording the clock time of the first measurement), it was not straightforward to estimate the delay when receiving the synchronization signal. However, a conservative estimate of 2 s has been obtained using the available data. Considering the physics of the flow, the uncertainty contribution of this delay is supposed to be larger if the flow rate undergoes relatively large changes from unstable flow conditions during this time. We therefore estimate the uncertainty contribution due to the delay as

$$\frac{\text{delay}}{\text{batch time}} \frac{\text{std}(\text{flow rate})}{\text{avg}(\text{flow rate})}$$

where we use the within run standard deviation of the flow rate as an indicator of the amplitude of the changes undergone by the flow rate. The value of this uncertainty source varies among the runs and it is about 0.01%. We treat this estimate as the standard deviation of a normal distribution. The second uncertainty contribution due to the synchronization timing is caused by the different sampling interval of the two systems. We estimate such uncertainty component as

$$\frac{|\text{sampling interval CMF} - \text{sampling interval turbine}|}{\text{total mass}}$$

which we consider as the half-width of a uniform distribution. Its value ranges between 0.03% and 0.09% with higher values at higher flow rates.

Lastly, when calculating the deviations of the meter under test, the reference meter is usually corrected for its known deviations in the measurements at process conditions. However, by lack of a SI-traceable calibration directly on LH₂, in this case it is not possible to know the deviation of the transfer standard at LH₂ conditions with sufficient corroboration. Therefore, by extrapolating from the known errors determined from direct calibration on LNG and recognizing it to fall within the uncertainties predicted from the model equations (2),

Table 4
Uncertainty components of the total standard uncertainty budget of the on-site calibration uncertainty.

Uncertainty component	Probability distribution	Standard uncertainty contribution (%)
Density model uncertainty	normal	0.18
Repeatability	normal	0.07
On-site density uncertainty	normal	0.57
Delay in synchronization signal	normal	0.01
Different sampling interval	normal	0.09
Deviations at process conditions	uniform	$0.40/\sqrt{3}$
Total on-site standard uncertainty	normal	0.65

Fig. 4. Example of the mass flow measurements during one of the batches. The red line displays the measurements as calculated using the stiffness method (2), while the blue line has been obtained using the density correction method (3). It can be noted that the density corrected measurements are systematically smaller than the values obtained using the correction based on the Young’s modulus. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

and (3), we estimate an error of 0.4 % at LH₂ conditions which we treat as the half-width of a uniform distribution. We then combine it with the other uncertainty sources using the law of propagation of uncertainty [26]. From the above, we obtained a base uncertainty of the reference standard for the on-site calibration at LH₂ process conditions of 0.65 % ($k = 1$) for the raw errors based on totalized mass (see Table 4).

4. Results

Looking at the mass flow measurements during a batch (Fig. 4), it is possible to notice that the stiffness correction model yields consistently higher flow rate values with respect to the density correction model. We note that in this application, the stiffness correction model was used beyond its range since it is being applied to measurements that were executed at temperatures lower than -233 °C. Therefore the approximation used to account for the Young’s modulus effect might not be as accurate at temperatures below the stated range of validity of the model. The difference in the totalized mass is about 0.73 % for each repeat with an associated standard uncertainty of 0.55 % ($k = 1$), see Fig. 5. The uncertainty has been estimated by propagation of the uncertainties of the density and of the stiffness correction model via the Monte Carlo method [17] through the raw error equation (see Appendix A). The 95 % confidence interval of the difference between the two correction models contains zero, thus the difference between the two correction models is not statistically significant and the measurement results obtained with the two models can be said to be in agreement.

Fig. 5. Relative error between the CMF measurements corrected using Eq. (2) and the measurements corrected using Eq. (3). The results obtained with Eq. (3) have been considered as reference. The error bars denote the 95 % confidence interval ($k = 2$).

Table 5

Overview of run time, totalized mass values and relative errors on the totalized mass where the values obtained with the density model have been considered as reference. The standard uncertainty of the relative errors is 0.55 % ($k = 1$) for the errors between the two CMF correction models, and 0.67 % ($k = 1$) for the errors between the CMF density corrected measurement data and the turbine measurements results.

Repeat #	Run time		Totalized mass			Relative errors	
	CMF s	Turbine meter s	CMF stiffness model kg	CMF density model kg	Turbine meter kg	Stiffness vs Density %	Turbine vs CMF %
1	29.407	29.220	22.78	22.62	23.18	0.71	2.45
2	43.107	42.959	21.43	21.27	21.85	0.73	2.72
3	84.949	84.796	27.86	27.66	28.34	0.74	2.45
4	33.838	33.579	26.32	26.13	26.64	0.70	1.96
5	63.250	63.110	31.70	31.48	32.24	0.72	2.44
6	93.479	93.220	31.21	30.99	31.63	0.73	2.03
7	34.569	34.442	26.68	26.49	27.18	0.70	2.58
8	64.801	64.650	32.01	31.78	32.62	0.72	2.63
9	91.952	91.807	30.46	30.24	30.91	0.73	2.20
10	32.814	32.769	25.30	25.13	25.84	0.70	2.82
11	48.241	48.078	23.85	23.68	24.26	0.72	2.45
12	104.162	104.000	34.52	34.26	35.00	0.75	2.13
13	91.567	91.422	30.39	30.15	30.83	0.79	2.28
14	61.593	61.409	30.68	30.44	31.27	0.78	2.73
15	34.407	34.312	26.68	26.48	27.24	0.75	2.85

Fig. 6. Relative error in totalized mass between the CMF measurements corrected using Eq. (3) and the measurements of the turbine meters. The CMF’s measurements have been considered as reference. The error bars denote the 95 % confidence interval ($k = 2$).

When comparing the combined measurements of the turbine meters with the CMF measurements, errors between 2.0 % and 2.9 % with associated standard uncertainty of about 0.67 % ($k = 1$) have been observed in the totalized mass, see Table 5. These results have been obtained by propagating the on-site calibration uncertainty via the Monte Carlo method through the raw error equation. Thus the turbine meter is significantly overestimating the totalized mass. The mean raw error on the totalized mass is 2.22 %, 2.60 % and 2.66 % with estimated repeatability uncertainty of 0.07 %, 0.06 % and 0.10 % for setpoints 0.35 kg/s, 0.50 kg/s and 0.80 kg/s, respectively. We approximate the repeatability uncertainty as $u_{repeat} = 0.07$ %. Lastly, we note that the errors show a dependency on the flow rate, where lower deviations are recorded at the lower flow rates, see Fig. 6.

5. Discussion

The results show that the two correction methods for CMF measurements agree to each other within the stated uncertainty (even though

the stiffness model was applied beyond its stated validity range). However, it is worth noting that the stiffness correction method has a larger uncertainty (most of which is due to the uncertainty in the measurements of the Young’s modulus) and consistently estimates a higher value with respect to the values obtained with the density correction method. More accurate measurements of the Young’s modulus (and, potentially, a more accurate approximation of the Young’s modulus at temperatures below -233 °C) would help to reduce the uncertainty of the stiffness correction method, and it could possibly reduce the difference between the measurement values obtained with the two correction methods. In any case, in order to obtain full direct traceability and to establish which of the two correction models is closer to the true value, a dedicated LH₂ flow standard with direct traceability to SI-units is necessary.

In a similar fashion as described in Section 3, it is possible to derive an uncertainty budget of the density correction method when applied to LNG measurements. We note that many of the uncertainty components remain the same as some uncertainty contributions seen during LNG calibration have been used as proxy for LH₂ measurements. The uncertainty components that should be modified are the zero stability (the minimum flow tested during the LNG calibration was 0.497 kg/s), the uncertainty due to the pressure correction (during the LNG measurements there was no set pressure, thus the uncertainty in the correction is due to the uncertainty of the pressure measurement and of the pressure correction factor), the uncertainty in the temperature measurement (in this case we consider a uniform distribution with half-width of 3 K), and the uncertainty in the density estimate. To estimate the uncertainty contribution due to density, we propagate temperature and pressure uncertainty through the GERG-2008 EOS [33] instead of the equation of state by Leachman et al. [25], since the latter is valid only for hydrogen and the former is indicated in ISO 20765 part 2 [34] as a suitable equation of state for the calculation of the thermodynamic properties of natural gas. The so estimated standard uncertainty of the density correction model for LNG measurements is thus 0.14 % ($k = 1$), to which we add the repeatability uncertainty recorded during the LNG measurements, i.e. $u_{repeat} = 0.019$ %, to obtain an on-site calibration uncertainty of 0.14 % ($k = 1$). We note that in this case there is no uncertainty due to the synchronization timing since the same data acquisition system has been used to record the measurement data of both instruments (i.e., the CMF and the facility’s master meter). Furthermore there is no uncertainty contribution due to the on-site density estimation since both the CMF and the facility’s master meter measurement results are based on mass flow rate. The errors for LNG measurements are computed using the facility’s references, with an associated standard uncertainty of 0.09 % ($k = 1$) (the facility has an uncertainty of 0.17 % ($k = 2$) for mass flow measurements). The

comparison between the CMF measurement results and those of VSL's calibration facility show errors in the CMF's measurements between -0.23% and -0.26% (see Fig. 1) with an associated standard uncertainty of 0.09% ($k = 1$). These errors fall within the 95% confidence interval identified by the uncertainty associated to the density model for LNG measurements, i.e. $\pm 0.28\%$ ($k = 2$), although they are rather close to the lower boundary of the confidence interval. Furthermore we note that the errors have similar values for each setpoint and do not behave as a random error. We thus consider this error as a systematic effect in the CMF measurements and include an additional uncertainty source in the uncertainty budget for LH_2 measurements as described in Section 3.4. Lastly, we remark that this interpretation is based on limited samples and additional testing is required to further investigate this.

The comparison of the LH_2 measurement results given by the turbine and the CMF meters reveals errors on totalized mass ranging from 2.0% to 2.9% with a standard uncertainty of about 0.67% ($k = 1$). The error uncertainty does not explain the measured difference between the meters, revealing thus that this error is significantly different from zero and that the turbine meters tend to overestimate the totalized mass with respect to the reference CMF measurements. From the legal metrology point of view, LNG measuring systems fall within accuracy class 1.5 [35], which requires the flow meter to have a maximum permissible error of 1.0% . If LH_2 measuring systems will be expected to be in the same accuracy class, the uncertainty calculated here is still too large to comply with the legal requirements and more work is necessary to reduce the measurement uncertainty.

6. Conclusions

This study indicates that, the achievable base standard uncertainty for LH_2 mass flow rate measurement by a CMF lies within range 0.2% – 0.5% relative (see Section 3.3). This study further indicates that by combining alternative fluid calibrations and CMF modeling, it is possible to obtain an estimated uncertainty of 1.34% ($k = 2$) on totalized mass when measuring the flow rate of liquefied hydrogen using volume based and mass based flow rate measurements (see Table 4). The main uncertainty source was identified as the on-site density estimation necessary to convert the volume flow measurements into mass flow measurements. The calibration uncertainty is likely to be lower when comparing meters both measuring mass (or volume) flow rate. The results further indicate the need for reliable and accurate temperature measurements (the latter allowing for an accurate density estimate), so that volume based (turbine, ultrasonic) and mass based (Coriolis) amount measurements in LH_2 custody transfer processes can be compared with smaller uncertainties. Further proving by dedicated LNG and LH_2 flow standards, with direct link to the SI-units, is needed to substantiate these findings.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Federica Gugole: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Menne D. Schakel:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Aleksandr Druzhkov:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Maarten Brugman:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Maarten Brugman reports a relationship with Emerson that includes: employment. Aleksandr Druzhkov reports a relationship with Emerson that includes: employment. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Mathematical definition of the raw error

The raw error is calculated according to the following formula

$$e = \frac{Q_{cand} - Q_{ref}}{Q_{ref}}$$

where Q_{cand} [SI-unit: kg] and Q_{ref} [kg] are the totalized mass of the candidate and of the reference meter respectively. When comparing the two correction models, Q_{cand} is selected as the totalized mass obtained applying the stiffness correction model to the CMF's measurement results, while in the data processing for the on-site calibration Q_{cand} is given by the totalized mass measured by the combined turbine meters. In both cases Q_{ref} is given by the totalized mass measured by the CMF's measurement results corrected by means of the density method.

Appendix B. Supplementary data

Data will be made available on request.

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